
Rotenone-Based Management of Invasive Fish at DTW: A Feasibility Analysis Using Chemical Dynamics Modeling

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Purpose:

This project modeled rotenone decay and mass-balance dynamics to evaluate the feasibility of using chemical treatment to manage invasive fish in DTW retention ponds—and ultimately, help reduce uncertainty in relevant structured decision-making processes.

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Pictured above, observations from natural winter goldfish mortality at DTW, 2016–2025.

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Executive Summary

- **Invasive goldfish populations in DTW retention ponds represent a long-standing management problem (10+ years)** due to their role in attracting hazardous bird species, highlighting the need to identify feasible and effective fish-management options.
- **Rotenone treatment was determined to be operationally feasible at DTW.** Based on modeled decay timelines, hydrologic constraints, and staffing considerations, the DTW Pond and Fish Workgroup (WCAA's Airfield Operations Department–Wildlife Division and Environmental Department) concluded that rotenone application was a feasible invasive fish management option.
- **Under conservative assumptions, regulatory thresholds were reached within approximately one workweek.** Decay–dilution modeling indicated that rotenone concentrations declined below the regulatory threshold of 2 ppb within approximately 4–7 days post-treatment, depending on pond hydrology.
- **Our model-averaged rotenone half-life at DTW was approximately 1.5 days.** Using published rotenone degradation data integrated with DTW-specific pond temperature and pH measurements, we consistently estimated half-life values ranging from 1–2 days across all four candidate models.
- **Our model-averaged half-life represents a conservative estimate of persistence.** DTW temperature data did not include peak daily conditions, and some supporting literature was derived from larger water bodies where degradation is slower. Empirical studies from shallow Midwestern ponds suggest true rotenone half-life at DTW may be closer to one day or less (Gilderhus et al. 1986, 1988).
- **Pond-specific hydrology strongly influenced treatment timelines.** Differences in storage capacity and dilution potential among ponds substantially affected time to non-detectable concentrations (<2 ppb), highlighting the importance of site-specific volume estimates.
- **Our modeling framework provides a reproducible, decision-support tool.** Model parameters allow practitioners to evaluate rotenone decay under alternative environmental conditions—simply put, updating temperature and pH values in our equations can allow general approximation of rotenone half-life.
- **Any rotenone application must adhere strictly to product-label requirements—and the *Planning and Standard Operating Procedures for the Use of Rotenone in Fish Management* (SOP; Finlayson et al. 2018).** Our analyses were conducted to inform feasibility and reduce uncertainty, whereas on-the-ground rotenone implementation would require full compliance with label instructions, SOP guidance, permitting conditions, and site-specific operational planning.

Introduction

Abundant invasive goldfish (*Carassius auratus*) in retention ponds at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) have been identified as a persistent wildlife-hazard concern because they attract piscivorous (fish-eating) birds that are strongly associated with damaging aircraft strikes, including double-crested cormorants (*Nannopterum auritum*), gulls (*Larus* spp.), osprey (*Pandion haliaetus*), and bald eagles (*Haliaeetus leucocephalus*). In response, the DTW Pond and Fish Workgroup was established to develop a coordinated, long-term strategy to reduce fish abundance in stormwater ponds and thereby decrease their attractiveness to hazardous bird species while also improving pond function and water quality. Rotenone is one potential management tool capable of achieving complete fish eradication in impoundments—an outcome that nonchemical methods, although often lower cost and more publicly acceptable (e.g., electrofishing, seine netting), typically do not achieve in isolation (Finlayson et al. 2018). In addition to fish removal, rotenone treatments have been shown to improve water quality by eliminating sediment-suspending fishes (e.g., goldfish), resulting in improved water quality (Prejs et al. 1997, Eilers et al. 2011).

Rotenone effectiveness and environmental persistence are strongly influenced by site-specific water chemistry and hydrology. Temperature is generally considered the dominant driver of rotenone degradation, although pH also plays an important role, with reported rotenone half-life values varying inversely with water temperature and pH—and faster degradation occurring under warmer and more basic conditions (Thomas 1983; Finlayson et al. 2001, 2014; Vasquez et al. 2012). In shallow ponds comparable to DTW's, rotenone half-life has been estimated at approximately one day (Gilderhus et al. 1986, 1988). Under typical pond and lake conditions, rotenone is expected to detoxify through natural dissipation processes within approximately one week to one month, depending on environmental conditions (Finlayson et al. 2018). However, the use of rotenone in operational stormwater systems requires careful evaluation of chemical persistence, hydrologic dynamics, and regulatory discharge constraints, particularly in highly managed environments like airports.

Accordingly, the purpose of this study was to model rotenone decay under DTW-specific conditions to evaluate the feasibility of chemical treatment for managing invasive goldfish in retention ponds. Specifically, our objectives were to (1) characterize plausible rotenone decay rates across relevant temperature and pH conditions, (2) quantify the influence of dilution associated with stormwater management on post-treatment concentrations, and (3) estimate the time required for rotenone concentrations to decline below regulatory thresholds under conservative planning scenarios. Collectively, these

analyses were intended to reduce uncertainty and provide relevant information to support structured decision-making processes evaluating rotenone alongside alternative invasive fish management strategies at DTW.

Methods

Site-condition estimation

We used empirical data to parameterize pond-site conditions for input into our chemical-dynamics modeling framework. First, we digitized logbook records maintained by the WCAA Environmental Department and restricted the dataset to the three most recent years to preserve temporal relevance and reporting consistency (data retrieved May 2025; Appendix A). We focused on water temperature and pH data, the primary environmental determinants of rotenone degradation kinetics (Gilderhus et al. 1988, Finlayson et al. 2001, 2014, Vasquez et al. 2012, Finlayson et al. 2018). Data coverage was most complete for Pond 3E—the airfield’s primary discharge pond and the site with the highest frequency of fish observations and associated avian predation risks to aircraft operations—making it the most appropriate basin for model parameterization. Because the planned treatment window was anticipated for midsummer, we restricted the dataset to July and August to ensure that modeled degradation processes reflected the environmental conditions expected during implementation (e.g., water temperature).

Decay-curve development

Literature-derived data integration

We used published data to model rotenone half-life in our study system. First, we conducted a targeted literature review to compile empirical data from studies reporting rotenone degradation estimates alongside relevant environmental covariates such as water temperature and pH. Because our aim was to obtain representative decay information rather than perform a systematic review, we did not apply formal search criteria, date restrictions, or structured screening procedures; instead, studies were selected opportunistically while balancing time constraints. From these studies (lake, pond, and laboratory systems), we extracted reported or calculated median values to serve as inputs for decay-curve development. Using these cross-study degradation data, we fitted decay curves to parameterize the chemical-dynamics modeling framework used in our analysis.

Exponential-decay models

We built two exponential-decay models to model the rotenone decay process directly. This was a nonlinear approach which followed first-order kinetics. Both exponential-decay models used incorporated temperature data and did not include pH—as more studies had water temperature data than pH, given its strong influence on rotenone degradation. The first candidate exponential-decay model, the pond-temperature model, used data from literature restricted to pond studies—which we considered to be the most comparable to our water management system at DTW—and closest to the assumed site conditions during the anticipated treatment. The second of these candidate models, the lake-and-pond temperature model, incorporated temperature data from lakes and ponds. Our intention with this second model was to capture more extreme conditions if the water were deeper, to be on the safe and conservative side and have a range of potential outcomes.

Chemical degradation processes such as rotenone hydrolysis typically follow first-order kinetics (e.g., Dawson et al. 1991, Vasquez et al. 2012), an approach widely applied in environmental toxicology, water chemistry, and pharmacokinetics. Accordingly, our exponential-decay modeling framework was grounded in standard first-order chemical-kinetics equations (Equations 1–4). Concentration over time followed the first-order decay function

$$C(t) = C_0 e^{-kt}, \quad (1)$$

where $C(t)$ is concentration at time t , C_0 is initial concentration, k is the first-order decay rate, and e is the base of the natural logarithm (i.e., Euler's constant). The corresponding relationship between decay rate and half-life was

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln(2)}{k}, \quad (2)$$

which links $t_{1/2}$ directly to k . To incorporate environmental effects, we modeled half-life as a temperature-dependent function,

$$t_{1/2}(T) = \alpha e^{\beta T}, \quad (3)$$

which allows half-life to vary with water temperature T according to the α baseline half-life scaling parameter and the β temperature-sensitivity coefficient (describing how half-life changes with temperature). Substituting Equation 3 into Equation 2 yielded a temperature-dependent decay rate,

$$k(T) = \frac{\ln(2)}{\alpha e^{\beta T}}, \quad (4)$$

defining the decay rate at a given temperature. Together, these equations describe concentration dynamics as a function of time, initial concentration C_0 , decay rate k , half-life $t_{1/2}$, water temperature T , and temperature-dependence parameters α and β .

Log-linear models

We also developed two log-linear candidate models to estimate rotenone half-life as a function of environmental predictors (Equations 5 and 6), rather than modeling the decay process directly. This approach allowed us to incorporate multiple environmental covariates—specifically temperature and pH—into a single predictive framework, providing a flexible and statistically robust way to quantify how site conditions may influence rotenone persistence. The first model—the full temperature-and-pH model—included all available data from lakes, ponds, and laboratory studies. The second model—the restricted temperature-and-pH model—used a restricted subset of observations that more closely matched the environmental conditions expected in DTW’s ponds during anticipated rotenone treatment (July or August). This subset included only records with pH between 7.5 and 9 and water temperatures above 40 °F, and excluded data obtained under laboratory conditions, which we considered less representative of realized field conditions. We modeled rotenone half-life using a log-linear regression of the form

$$\ln(t_{1/2}) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T + \beta_2 \text{pH} + \varepsilon, \quad (5)$$

where $t_{1/2}$ is half-life (days), T is water temperature (°F), pH is water acidity or alkalinity, β_0 , β_1 , and β_2 are regression coefficients estimated from the data, and ε is the error term. We predicted half-life values by exponentiating the linear predictor,

$$\hat{t}_{1/2} = \exp(\beta_0 + \beta_1 T + \beta_2 \text{pH}), \quad (6)$$

returning estimates on the original scale of days. Note that predicted effects were obtained by varying one predictor while holding the other at its mean value. We considered predictors to have statistically significant effects on half-life when associated p-values were less than 0.01.

Model-averaged half-life estimation

To integrate predictions across our four candidate models (two exponential-decay models and two log-linear models), we implemented a simple model-averaging approach to generate a unified estimate of rotenone half-life under the anticipated site conditions. For each model, we predicted half-life at the mean summer water temperature and, where applicable, the corresponding mean summer pH. We then averaged these model-specific estimates to represent the central tendency across modeling approaches.

Because our objective was to capture the range of plausible decay outcomes rather than formally weight models using information criteria, we used an unweighted arithmetic mean of the four half-life predictions. To characterize uncertainty among models, we calculated the standard deviation (SD) of the model-specific estimates, providing a measure of between-model variability. This SD reflected how differences in predictor sets, data sources, and environmental filters influenced predicted rotenone persistence. Together, our average estimate and associated SD summarized the expected half-life and uncertainty across all candidate models.

To aid interpretation of the model-averaged half-life estimate, we also generated a conceptual decay curve representing expected rotenone behavior under average site conditions at DTW. This curve was based on first-order chemical kinetics (Equations 1–4) and parameterized using the model-averaged half-life derived from the four candidate models. Concentration was expressed as relative concentration, $C(t)$ divided by C_0 , to provide a dose-independent depiction of decay over time. The resulting curve illustrates the expected temporal decline in rotenone concentration given average DTW site conditions (midsummer), rather than representing predictions from any single fitted model.

Decay and dilution scenarios

To define realistic and regulatory-compliant decay and dilution scenarios, we referenced the *Planning and Standard Operating Procedures for the Use of Rotenone in Fish Management* (Finlayson et al. 2018), a joint U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service and American Fisheries Society publication that provides standardized operational, safety, and environmental procedures for rotenone applications. Rotenone product labels explicitly require that treatments be conducted in accordance with these Standard Operating Procedures, making this document the authoritative reference for treatment design, implementation, and post-treatment management.

In addition to environmental degradation of rotenone, we evaluated dilution scenarios relevant to stormwater management at DTW. As described by Finlayson et al. (2018), rotenone leaving a treatment area must be reduced to non-detectable levels (<2 ppb) prior to discharge to public waters—and treatment planning must account for both hydrologic conditions and potential water movement following application. At DTW, retention pond water levels can be actively manipulated by stormwater managers and may also change during the treatment period due to natural processes such as precipitation. For example, pond water levels may be drawn down in advance to increase available storage capacity and subsequently fill to maximum volume during a rain event, creating the potential for rapid dilution following treatment.

To ensure a conservative assessment consistent with SOP guidance, we modeled treatments using the maximum rotenone concentration allowed on the product label—200 ppb rotenone (equivalent to 4 ppm of a 5% active-ingredient formulation)—which represents the upper bound of legally permitted application rates in standing and flowing waters (Finlayson et al. 2018). Modeling the label maximum provides a worst-case scenario for estimating persistence and time required to reach regulatory discharge thresholds at DTW. We integrated the model-averaged decay rate (half-life estimate) with mass-balance modeling to simulate reductions in rotenone concentration under two scenarios: (1) natural first-order decay without dilution and (2) decay followed by instantaneous dilution associated with pond filling to maximum volume. To simulate these conditions, we integrated the first-order decay framework described by Equations 1–4 with mass-balance dilution modeling. Because most analyses focused on Pond 3E, we additionally performed decay–dilution simulations for Pond 3W to evaluate potential variability in outcomes associated with differences in pond hydrology—as other ponds may also be considered for treatment. Volume estimates for representative retention ponds were provided by the WCAA Environmental Department, reported in million gallons (MG), and reflect site-specific hydrologic conditions (data provided 04 April 2025).

Results from our decay simulations were reported as time-to-threshold estimates (i.e., days required to reach <2 ppb rotenone) and are visualized using decay–dilution curves illustrating expected concentration trajectories under site-specific conditions. These modeled outcomes were subsequently used to inform the feasibility evaluation by providing decision-relevant estimates of treatment duration, discharge timing, and the likelihood that rotenone concentrations would decline below regulatory thresholds within operational and staffing constraints at DTW.

Feasibility evaluation

We evaluated the feasibility of chemical treatment (rotenone) for invasive goldfish management at DTW by having WCAA staff assess its operational practicality given hydrologic constraints, logistical considerations, and discharge concerns. A primary constraint was the limited water-holding time available within DTW’s retention ponds: during rainfall events, restricted storage capacity can require timely discharge to public waters, creating substantial operational risk if treatment necessitates prolonged water retention while rotenone concentrations remain elevated. Logistical feasibility was also a key factor; treatments extending beyond a standard five-day workweek were considered impractical because they would require continuous staff availability from treatment initiation through completion. In addition, WCAA staff expressed a preference to minimize chemical inputs associated with treatment, as both rotenone and supplemental chemicals

raise concerns related to discharge to public waters and may trigger additional permitting requirements. Consequently, natural rotenone degradation was preferred over the use of chemical neutralizing agents (e.g., potassium permanganate).

Our feasibility determinations were made by WCAA’s Airfield Operations Department–Wildlife Division in collaboration with WCAA’s Environmental Department—who oversee stormwater management and serve as subject-matter experts in pond operations. Further, we made these determinations over a series of regularly scheduled DTW Pond and Fish Workgroup meetings. Based on hydrologic capacity, anticipated treatment duration, operational staffing requirements, and discharge considerations, the Workgroup evaluated rotenone treatment feasibility for the planning scenario and classified the option as either feasible or infeasible. This determination occurred within a broader structured decision-making process used to assess the feasibility of all invasive-fish management alternatives.

Results and Discussion

Site condition estimation

We estimated site conditions for Pond 3E using summer data (i.e., July and August), yielding 24 useable records. We found mean summer water temperature was 75.41 °F (SD: 3.06 °F), and mean pH was 7.99 (SD: 0.34; Table 1). Because our measurements were limited to working hours and discharge events, no data were collected during peak afternoon heat (15:00–17:00; Figure 1). As a result, our water temperature estimates likely underestimate actual conditions and thus provide conservative inputs for chemical modeling and treatment planning—especially given that higher water temperatures correspond to faster rotenone degradation (Finlayson et al. 2018).

Table 1. Site-condition estimates for water in Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport’s 3E retention pond during summer 2022–2024.

Variable	Minimum	Maximum	Average	SD
Temperature (°F)	70.70	80.96	75.41	3.06
pH	7.57	8.83	7.99	0.34

Figure 1. Density of water-sampling times for Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport’s 3E retention pond, summer 2022–2024. No sampling occurred during peak afternoon heat (15:00–17:00; 24 hr), meaning recorded temperatures likely underestimate true daily maxima and may be interpreted as conservative inputs for chemical modeling and treatment planning.

Decay-curve development

Literature-derived data integration

Our targeted literature review identified eight studies that reported rotenone degradation or half-life estimates under field or experimental conditions relevant to our analysis (Table 1). From these studies, we extracted 17 usable records (i.e., rows of data), each representing an individual water body or experimental system. All records contained temperature data and half-life information suitable for modeling, whereas pH values were available for 11 of the 17 records, constraining the sample size available for temperature–pH log-linear modeling. Our compiled dataset spanned a range of system types and depths, including four shallow pond records (<3.28 ft [<1 m] deep), seven lake records, three additional pond records, and three laboratory-based experiments. This diversity provided broad coverage of environmental conditions influencing rotenone persistence, while also allowing subsets of the data to be filtered to more closely match DTW’s retention-pond characteristics. Notably, several of the identified studies were sourced from the American Fisheries Society’s Rotenone Stewardship Program Rotenone Library, which served as a valuable centralized repository of peer-reviewed articles and government reports relevant to rotenone (AFS 2025).

Together, our literature-derived data formed the empirical basis for both the exponential-decay models, which relied on temperature and half-life relationships across all records, and the log-linear temperature–pH models, which were limited to observations containing complete covariate information. Although variability in reported covariates (temperature, pH) reduced the number of observations available for some model classes, the compiled dataset captured a realistic range of environmental conditions under which rotenone degradation has been observed, supporting subsequent decay-curve development and DTW site-specific half-life estimation.

Table 2. Relevant rotenone half-life data extracted from published literature, including water temperature, pH, half-life estimates (days), general waterbody classification, and reference source. These values informed development of our decay curves used in rotenone treatment modeling for Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport’s (DTW) retention ponds. Note that the shallow pond classification reflected study systems with water depths <3.28 feet (<1 meter), which closely approximated DTW conditions.

Reported water temp (°C)	Median water temp (°F)	Recorded pH	Median pH	Half-life estimate (days)	Waterbody classification	Reference
24	75.2	8.9	8.9	0.58	Shallow pond	Gilderhus et al. 1986
0	32	NA	NA	3.5	Shallow pond	Gilderhus et al. 1986
23–27	77	8.35	8.35	0.94	Shallow pond	Gilderhus et al. 1988
0–5	36.5	8.62	8.62	10.3	Shallow pond	Gilderhus et al. 1988
19	66.2	9.8	9.8	1.2	Lake	Campbell and Ruppel 2006
17–18	63.5	9.7	9.7	4.5	Lake	Finlayson et al. 2014
20–22	69.8	7.6–7.7	7.65	1.7	Lake	Finlayson et al. 2001
10–22	60.8	8.3	8.3	3.5	Lake	Finlayson et al. 2001
5–12	47.3	7.5–9.2	8.35	7.7	Lake	Finlayson et al. 2001
8	46.4	NA	NA	1.8	Pond	Dawson et al. 1991
22	76.1	NA	NA	0.7	Pond	Dawson et al. 1991
15	59	NA	NA	1.8	Pond	Dawson et al. 1991
25	77	5	5	12.6	Lab setting	Thomas 1983
25	77	7	7	3.2	Lab setting	Thomas 1983
25	77	9	9	2	Lab setting	Thomas 1983
13.5	56.3	NA	NA	7.7	Lake	McMillin and Finlayson 2008
17.2	62.96	NA	NA	5.6	Lake	McMillin and Finlayson 2008

Exponential-decay models

We modeled rotenone degradation using two exponential-decay models and found that predicted half-life ranged from approximately 1–2 days depending on the modeling approach. Our pond-temperature model, based solely on pond-derived observations most representative of DTW’s treatment environment, estimated a relatively rapid half-life of 0.97 days at the mean summer water temperature (75.41 °F; Figure 2). Our results were consistent with studies of shallow Midwestern ponds, suggesting that the effective rotenone half-life at DTW is likely on the order of one day or less (Gilderhus et al. 1986, 1988). Although these studies informed model development, the resulting estimates aligned closely with independent empirical observations from similar systems. In contrast, our lake-and-pond temperature model predicted a more conservative half-life of 2.25 days, reflecting the broader range of water temperatures represented in the combined dataset (Figure 2).

The number of observations informing each model also differed, with the lake-and-pond dataset containing twice as many data points ($n = 14$) as the pond-only dataset ($n = 7$), which may partially explain the greater variability and more moderate temperature response in the combined model (Table 3). From a management perspective, these differences emphasize the sensitivity of half-life predictions to temperature conditions and data sources: warmer, shallow pond environments—such as those at DTW—are expected to promote faster rotenone degradation, whereas deeper or cooler systems yield more conservative (longer) persistence estimates. Together, the two models bracket a plausible range of degradation rates relevant to DTW’s operational conditions.

Parameter estimates from the exponential-decay models were consistent with temperature-driven degradation, with negative β values in both cases. The pond-temperature model had a more negative β (-0.0439 ; $\alpha = 26.581$) than the lake-and-pond model (-0.0270 ; $\alpha = 17.284$), indicating a steeper temperature response and correspondingly faster degradation under pond-like conditions such as those at DTW. It is important to note that these exponential model estimates for the α baseline half-life scaling parameter and the β temperature-sensitivity coefficient can also be used to calculate temperature-dependent decay rates for other water temperatures (e.g., by substituting values into Equation 4).

Figure 2. Rotenone decay curves (green lines) estimated using empirical data and exponential-decay models incorporating water temperature, based on (a) pond-only studies and (b) combined lake-and-pond studies. Black points represent individual records (literature-based), and the equations displayed show the temperature-dependent decay functions used to estimate half-life. Across models, estimated half-lives ranged from approximately 1–2 days, with degradation occurring more rapidly under the pond-only model.

Log-linear models

Our log-linear models produced half-life estimates broadly consistent with the exponential-decay models, with predictions ranging from approximately 1–2 days under DTW site conditions. In the full temperature-and-pH model, both temperature and pH exhibited statistically significant negative effects on log-transformed half-life ($\beta_1 = -0.0546$, $p = 0.0058$; $\beta_2 = -0.4993$, $p = 0.0096$; Table 3), indicating that rotenone degraded more rapidly at higher temperatures and higher pH values (more basic conditions; Figure 3). Applying these coefficients to the observed summer site conditions in Pond 3E (75.41 °F; pH 7.99) produced a predicted half-life of 1.96 days. Because this model incorporated all available observations with complete temperature and pH data, these results offer a conservative estimate of rotenone persistence across a wide range of conditions.

Our restricted temperature-and-pH model, which limited the dataset to values resembling DTW's broad field conditions (40–80 °F; pH 7–9), predicted a shorter half-life of 1.06 days, closely aligning with our pond-specific exponential-decay model. In this log-linear model, the temperature effect was statistically significant and strongly negative ($\beta_1 = -0.0789$, $p = 0.016$), whereas the pH coefficient was weaker and statistically uncertain ($\beta_2 = -0.5016$, $p = 0.21$), likely reflecting both the small sample size ($n = 5$; Table 3) and the relatively narrow pH range (7–9), over which pH effects on rotenone degradation may be limited. Our restricted temperature-and-pH model therefore likely provides a more realistic representation of rotenone degradation under the warm, shallow conditions typical of DTW's retention ponds, whereas the full model reflects broader environmental variability and yields a more conservative persistence estimate. Together, the log-linear models reinforce the dominant role of temperature in shaping rotenone degradation rates (Thomas 1983; Gilderhus et al. 1986, 1988; Dawson et al. 1991; Finlayson et al. 2001; McMillin and Finlayson 2008) and indicate that, under DTW's summertime conditions, half-life is expected to remain near or below a conservative two days.

Table 3. Parameter estimates for our four candidate rotenone decay models used to predict half-life under Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport’s (DTW) site conditions. Exponential-decay model results include estimates for the baseline half-life scaling parameter (α) and the temperature-sensitivity coefficient (β). Log-linear model results include the intercept (β_0) and coefficients for temperature (β_1) and pH (β_2) derived from linear models fit to log-transformed half-life. Sample size indicates the number of observations informing each model. Collectively, the parameter estimates show consistently negative temperature effects across all models, indicating that rotenone degrades rapidly under the warm summer conditions typical of DTW’s stormwater retention ponds.

Model	Sample size	Parameter estimates	Interpretation of results
Pond-temperature exponential model	7	$\alpha = 26.581$ $\beta = -0.0439$	Strong temperature sensitivity; faster degradation under warm pond conditions
Lake-and-pond exponential model	14	$\alpha = 17.284$ $\beta = -0.0270$	More moderate temperature response reflecting cooler and deeper systems
Full temperature-pH log-linear model	11	$\beta_0 = 8.7855$ $\beta_1 = -0.0546$ $\beta_2 = -0.4993$	Both temperature and pH strongly reduce half-life; broad, conservative model
Restricted temperature-pH log-linear model	5	$\beta_0 = 10.0210$ $\beta_1 = -0.0789$ $\beta_2 = -0.5016$	Strong temperature effect in DTW-like conditions; pH effect weaker

Figure 3. Predicted effects of water temperature and pH on rotenone half-life estimated using log-linear models. Panels show results for (a) the restricted temperature-and-pH model, which included only observations within field-relevant temperature and pH ranges, and (b) the full temperature-and-pH model, which incorporated all available data. Lines represent model-predicted half-life values (pH in blue and temperature in violet), with shaded bands indicating 95% confidence intervals, obtained by varying one predictor while holding the other at its dataset mean. Points represent literature-derived observations used to fit the models; axis scales vary among panels. Together, the log-linear models demonstrate that rotenone degradation accelerates with increasing temperature and pH, with temperature exerting the strongest and most consistent influence across modeling approaches, particularly under warm, pond-like conditions such as those at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport.

Model-averaged half-life estimation

We estimated a model-averaged rotenone half-life of 1.56 days under anticipated site conditions at DTW (75.41 °F; pH 7.99), with a between-model standard deviation of 0.56 days, reflecting variability attributable to differences in model structure, predictor sets, and underlying data sources (Figure 4). Across our four candidate models—two exponential-decay models and two log-linear models—we estimated half-life values ranging from 0.97 to 2.25 days, indicating relatively rapid rotenone degradation across all modeling approaches. Collectively, our candidate models estimated relatively rapid rotenone half-lives that fall within the broad range reported across diverse aquatic systems (<1–10 days; Thomas 1983; Gilderhus et al. 1986, 1988; Dawson et al. 1991; Finlayson et al. 2001, 2014; Campbell and Ruppel 2006; McMillin and Finlayson 2008). Although these empirical studies informed model development, the close agreement between modeled estimates and published values provides independent support that our models were performing as intended. Together, the model-averaged estimate and associated variability provide a unified, decision-relevant summary of expected rotenone persistence at DTW while explicitly acknowledging uncertainty across alternative modeling frameworks.

Figure 4. Model-averaged rotenone decay curve illustrating expected concentration dynamics under average site conditions at Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW). To provide a dose-independent depiction of decay over time, concentration is expressed relative to the initial concentration. These results represent a synthesis across modeling approaches and are intended to illustrate expected rotenone decay behavior under DTW site-specific conditions.

Decay and dilution scenarios

We estimated that, under conservative assumptions of label-maximum rotenone concentration, half-life, and limited holding capacity, modeled decay–dilution scenarios resulted in rotenone concentrations falling below regulatory thresholds within 4–7 days post treatment, depending on pond hydrology (Figure 5). After two days of natural decay at the assigned minimum pond volume (i.e., 3-ft water depth), modeled concentrations declined from 200 ppb to 82.2 ppb in both ponds. Subsequent instantaneous dilution associated with pond filling to maximum volume produced substantially different post-flood concentrations depending on pond storage capacity.

For Pond 3W (minimum volume = 16.0 MG; maximum volume = 66.0 MG), we estimated a post-dilution rotenone concentration of 19.9 ppb, requiring an additional 5.18 days of decay to fall below 2 ppb (Figure 5). This decay-dilute-decay process resulted in a total estimated duration of 7.18 days from treatment initiation to reach the regulatory discharge threshold. In contrast, Pond 3E (minimum volume = 7.5 MG; maximum volume = 103.0 MG) exhibited a much greater dilution effect, with post-flood rotenone concentration reduced to 6.0 ppb. Under this scenario, we estimated that concentrations declined below 2 ppb after an additional 2.47 days of decay, corresponding to a decay-dilute-decay duration of 4.47 days (Figure 5). Together, these results demonstrate that pond-specific volume characteristics strongly mediate the time required for rotenone concentrations to reach non-detectable levels under otherwise identical treatment concentrations and decay assumptions, with important implications for operational feasibility and discharge timing at DTW.

Figure 5. Simulated rotenone decay-dilution-decay dynamics for two Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport (DTW) retention ponds (Pond 3E and Pond 3W). Curves show modeled rotenone concentration (ppb) over time assuming first-order decay governed by a model-averaged half-life of 1.56 days (blue lines). Rotenone was applied at an initial concentration of 200 ppb (maximum legal treatment concentration), followed by two days of natural decay at assigned minimum pond volume (approximately 3-ft water depth), after which an instantaneous dilution event (vertical dotted line) represents pond filling to maximum volume. Post-dilution concentrations then continue to decay according to first-order kinetics. The horizontal dotted line denotes the rotenone regulatory threshold of 2 ppb (0.002 ppm), and red “X” symbols indicate the modeled time at which concentrations fall below this threshold for each pond. These results highlight the combined influence of chemical degradation and dilution in reducing rotenone concentrations under DTW’s site-specific operational conditions.

Feasibility evaluation

After reviewing results from this study, the DTW Pond and Fish Workgroup determined that rotenone treatment was operationally feasible for invasive fish management at DTW under conservative planning assumptions, with feasibility primarily governed by pond-specific hydrology and discharge options. Modeled decay–dilution timelines indicated that regulatory thresholds (<2 ppb) can be reached within approximately 5–7 days across representative ponds, supporting treatment viability within operational and staffing constraints. Pond 3E reached non-detectable rotenone concentrations within approximately 5 days, aligning well with standard 5-day workweek operations and minimizing discharge risk. Pond 3W required a longer decay period (approximately 7 days) due to lower dilution capacity. However, the Workgroup still considered rotenone treatment in Pond 3W operationally manageable given available risk-mitigation options. In particular, water from Pond 3W can be drawn down to depths below 3 feet, routed to a water treatment facility, or transferred to other retention ponds, providing operational flexibility for managing elevated concentrations and reducing reliance on prolonged on-site holding or chemical neutralizing agents (e.g., potassium permanganate).

Limitations and considerations

Our analyses were based on relatively small, site-specific datasets from WCAA records and cross-study literature, and results should be interpreted in that context. Accurate implementation of rotenone treatments requires up-to-date information on stormwater basin area, bathymetry or water depth, pond volume, and corresponding chemical dosing and dilution capacity. Although we evaluated multiple modeling frameworks to capture a broad range of plausible decay outcomes, uncertainty remains. Consistent with standard operating procedures, site-specific validation of rotenone decay using actual pond water is recommended prior to treatment (Finlayson et al. 2018). Subsequent changes in water temperature, pH, or storage capacity (e.g., following dredging) should prompt reevaluation of decay and dilution timelines. In addition, operational planning must account for weather-related constraints, which are often required by permitting agencies; accordingly, short-term weather forecasting and modeling can play an important role in treatment planning (e.g., application of (e.g., National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration’s National Blend of Models v4.3 [NOAA 2025])).

Despite these considerations, the purpose of this study was not to predict a single deterministic outcome or to presuppose implementation, but to evaluate the feasibility of rotenone treatment by bounding realistic decay and dilution behavior under conservative assumptions. By integrating literature-derived decay models, site-specific hydrologic information, regulatory thresholds, and operational constraints within a structured

decision-making framework, we provide a transparent and reproducible assessment of whether rotenone treatment can be implemented in compliance with regulatory, operational, and safety requirements at DTW. Our results here may inform subsequent comparisons of rotenone alongside other invasive fish management alternatives, allowing feasibility, risk, and operational constraints to be weighed explicitly when identifying the most appropriate management strategy.

Ethics Statement

This research acknowledges the ethical considerations involved in the management and handling of fish and wildlife at airports. All management activities referenced in this study would be conducted under appropriate permits, including those issued by relevant federal and state agencies. These actions would be carried out in accordance with established legal and ethical guidelines and be aimed at protecting human life and ensuring aviation safety by mitigating the risk of wildlife-aircraft strikes. Our research does not endorse unnecessary harm to organisms and supports the use of non-lethal methods whenever feasible. Ethical management practices, including habitat modification and deterrence, are emphasized as primary strategies, with direct control considered only as a last resort and in full regulatory compliance.

Data Availability

The R code and data used for analyses in this study are available at the GitHub repository: https://github.com/Steven-M-Gurney/Fish_Chemical_Modeling. Note that some data used in this study may be sensitive and therefore may not be available with the R code.

Appendix A: Site-condition Records

Table A1. Digitized logbook records maintained by the Wayne County Airport Authority’s Environmental Department for Detroit Metropolitan Wayne County Airport’s 3E retention pond, 2022–2024. Measurements were collected during standard working hours and during pond-water discharge events.

Date	Time (24 hr)	Pond	Water temp °C	pH	Free board (ft)	Ambient temp °C
6/1/2022	1040	3E	25.3	8.14	5	23
6/9/2022	1100	3E	19.5	7.78	4.45	19
6/14/2022	1515	3E	24.7	8.69	5.6	18
7/25/2022	1340	3E	25.5	8.23	4.7	26
8/6/2022	1145	3E	27.2	7.97	5.1	22
8/23/2022	1100	3E	24.1	8.14	5	16
8/31/2022	1055	3E	22.1	7.71	5.3	15
9/22/2022	1125	3E	18.9	7.87	5.5	14
9/27/2022	1150	3E	14.1	8.34	5.8	9
9/30/2022	0745	3E	12.9	8.03	6.5	6
6/21/2023	1220	3E	24.1	8.65	4.1	24
6/27/2023	1225	3E	20.6	8.5	4.6	17
7/3/2023	0910	3E	23.2	8.83	3.4	27
7/17/2023	1205	3E	23.3	8.05	5.1	17
7/21/2023	1115	3E	23.9	8.09	3.1	18
7/25/2023	1115	3E	26.1	7.99	4.6	19
7/27/2023	1115	3E	24.3	7.57	4.8	22
7/31/2023	1115	3E	24.4	7.57	6	15
8/3/2023	1025	3E	25.1	7.69	5.2	18
8/7/2023	1120	3E	22.8	7.66	5.6	18
8/16/2023	0920	3E	21.6	7.7	4.3	26
8/20/2023	1340	3E	24.7	8.36	5.2	26
8/23/2023	1220	3E	22.5	8.4	4.8	19
8/24/2023	0750	3E	22	7.59	0.9	22
9/12/2023	1245	3E	21.3	8.34	5.3	17
9/28/2023	0900	3E	17.9	7.94	4.8	17
6/3/2024	0955	3E	21.4	8.29	3.8	21
6/11/2024	1430	3E	22	8.44	5.1	13
6/24/2024	0855	3E	24.5	7.88	4.45	22
6/26/2024	1110	3E	23.5	7.5	3.9	22
7/1/2024	0850	3E	21.7	7.78	3.3	19
7/8/2024	1010	3E	26.7	8.37	5	21
7/11/2024	1020	3E	21.5	8.11	4.5	18
7/22/2024	0905	3E	25	7.8	4.9	21
7/30/2024	1015	3E	26.2	7.68	5.5	22
8/8/2024	1200	3E	24.2	7.88	5.25	25
8/14/2024	1150	3E	24.5	7.98	5.5	25
8/26/2024	1120	3E	26.2	8.54	5.6	32
9/2/2024	0845	3E	22.3	8.19	4.4	18
9/26/2024	1140	3E	20.4	7.96	5.8	16

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